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SUREWAVE- Structural Reliable Offshore Floating PV Solution Integrating Circular Concrete Floating Breakwater

Title: Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Master Plan

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Dissemination level	
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SEN	SEN = Sensitive – limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
EU classified	EU classified – restraint – UE/EU-restricted, confidential, secret-UE/EU secret under Decision 2015/444
Deliverable type	
R:	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)
DEM:	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs
DEC:	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.
OTHER:	Software, technical diagram, etc.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The scope of the present document is to comply with Consortium Commitment Deliverable D8.2, namely “SUREWAVE Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Master Plan.” This deliverable includes the strategy based on communication measures, targeted audiences, and dissemination and exploitation routes. To be revised on M18. Associated to Task 8.2

Deliverable Review

Reviewer #1: Eirik Larsen			Reviewer #2: Balram Panjwani		
Answer	Comments	Type *	Answer	Comments	Type *
1. Is the deliverable in accordance with					
(i) The Description of Work?	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(ii) The international State of the Art?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<i>Not applicable for this deliverable</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	<i>Not applicable for this deliverable</i>	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
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(ii) That needs improvement of the writing by the originator of the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a
(iii) That need further work by the Partners responsible for the deliverable?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No	<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		<input type="checkbox"/> M <input type="checkbox"/> m <input type="checkbox"/> a

* Type of comments: M = Major comment; m = minor comment; a = advice

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Abbreviations

EU -	European Union
CINEA -	Climate, Infrastructure, and Environment Executive Agency
BRIDGE -	Cooperation between Horizon 2020 projects in the fields of smart grid, energy storage, islands, and digitalisation.
DECMP –	Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Master Plan
FPV -	Floating Photovoltaics
DMP –	Data Management Plan
FAIR -	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
WP –	Work Package
M(X) –	Month
D –	Deliverable
SIS -	Sunlit Sea
NGO -	Non-Governmental Organization
GDPR -	General Data Protection Regulations
KPI -	Key Performance Indicator
LCA -	Life-Cycle Assessment
i.e., -	‘That is’
e.g., -	‘For example’
SEO –	Search Engine Optimization
O&M -	Operation and Maintenance
R&D -	Research and Development
SDG -	Sustainable Development Goals
DOI -	Digital Object Identifier

1. Introduction

The purpose of the Dissemination, Exploitation, and Communication Master Plan (DECMP) is to define strategic measures surrounding our communications towards stakeholders of the SUREWAVE project. Suggestions are based on the strategic goals defined in the Grand Agreement. We intend to maximize the project's impact and results while ongoing but also post-completion. The plan should function as a tool for the consortium throughout the project to achieve unified strategic and tactical decision-making.

The distinction between target groups and stakeholders is briefly discussed, ensuring that the plan has a solid foundation. A holistic overview of those affected by the project is conducted, in addition to suggestions of tailored key messages that may apply during content production. To track progress, pre-defined key performance indicators are highlighted and categorised, enabling tracking from M6 and onwards. The data will be revisited in the document's second iteration (M18), marking a natural point for evaluation and adjustment of the campaign.

A comprehensive plan covering communication routes and tools is established, incorporating the previously identified interest groups.

Furthermore, the DECMP will briefly discuss the data collection plan and measures to collect and process findings, covered in deliverable D1.3 – Data Management Plan.

Purpose and scope

WP8.1 Tasks according to the Do A

The main objective of WP8 is to develop and implement a successful strategy for dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement. The goal is to exploit the project results to maximize the impact of the project outcome and ensure its legacy.

To establish a strategically sound communication plan, the specific goals of this impact strategy are taken into consideration:

Goal 1: Raising *awareness* and *informing* stakeholders on *results* and proposed approaches for technology providers and early adaptors in the offshore energy sector.

Goal 2: Engaging in a *dialogue* with stakeholders, to foster *exploitation opportunities* both for commercialization and further research based on SUREWAVE solutions.

Goal 3: Transferring knowledge to partners and stakeholders.

Goal 4: Increasing acceptance of the proposed technical solutions, in particular the potential environmental & cost benefits.

Goal 5: Replicating the SUREWAVE solutions beyond the project's lifetime based on suitable business models and exploitation pathways.

Target audience and stakeholders

The SUREWAVE project has a wide range of target audiences and essential stakeholders. In this section, we will distinguish between groups that are targeting through our measures and overall actors that have a stake in our work, i.e., stakeholders.

Definitions:

Target group: “The group of people that a policy or campaign is *hoping* to influence in some way”²

Stakeholder: “A stakeholder is any individual, group or organization that is influenced by (or influences) an organization’s actions. They have an interest in the organization and its performance.”³

It is fair to assume that stakeholders, internally and externally, will actively pursue information about the project at some point. It might be beneficial to think that every target group is a stakeholder, but not all stakeholders will be targeted groups. The overview illustrates the holistic approach of a company’s stakeholders:

Picture: Stakeholders are often divided into two groups, internal and external stakeholders.⁴

The main goal of the screening process is to incorporate a proactive communication strategy rather than a responsive approach. The consortium and the SUREWAVE project represent the EU and its’ research, which involves an added corporate social responsibility. Going through this discussion might appear trivial, but in many ways, it is a crucial piece of the motivation behind disseminating and communication activities. EU states that:

The actions of companies have significant impacts on the lives of citizens in the EU and around the world. Not just in terms of the products and services they offer or the jobs and

² Collins English Dictionary., “Definition of 'target group',” Collinsdictionary.com, Last modified March 2023, <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/target-group>.

³ Nick Barnley, “What is a stakeholder?,” Techtarger.com, Last modified January 2023, <https://www.techtarger.com/searchcio/definition/stakeholder>.

⁴ Nick Barnley, “Stakeholders are often divided into two groups, internal and external stakeholders,” Techtarger.com, Last modified January 2023, <https://www.techtarger.com/searchcio/definition/stakeholder>.

opportunities they create, but also in terms of working conditions, human rights, health, the environment, innovation, education and training⁵.

Highlighting the impact that our research may have, is a natural introduction to the planning document. We are therefore not merely thinking in terms of goals, but rather ethical obligations. From now on, we will refer to *stakeholders* instead of *target groups*. SUREWAVE will have the following list of stakeholders:

Stakeholder category	Description	Relevant clusters
Consortium members	The members of the project have a stake in the project, by being associated with it and the results and success of its research findings. Moreover, every consortium member involved in the project has their own communication requirements and external communication duties.	SINTEF, IFEU, MARIN, Clement Germany, Sunlit Sea, Ceit, ACCIONA
EU management and network	Involved EU bodies have an interest through the funds invested and time working with or alongside the program.	EU The Council, EU Commission, EU Parliament Other EU platforms (Solar Power Europe, Ocean Energy Europe), (ETIP Ocean), Naturesea-PV, BRIDGE
Policy makers & Standardization bodies.	Designs policies and regulations for the industry. 'Countries have already deployed a variety of policy options to promote renewables but the required scale-up can only be achieved through more effective and comprehensive policies.' ⁶	Local government, state agencies, legislatures, private sector. The Maritime Spatial Planning Directive
Non-governmental organizations (NGOs)	Organizations that are interested in preservation and sustainability of operations - how the research and technical aspects may affect nature, animals and resources.	CERES , Conservation International (CI), Greenpeace , Natural Resources Defence Council (NRDC), The Nature Conservancy

⁵ European Commission, "Corporate social responsibility & Responsible business conduct," Commission.europa.eu, Last modified March 2023, https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/sustainability/corporate-social-responsibility-responsible-business-conduct_en.

⁶ IEA, "20 Renewable Energy Policy Recommendations," IEA, Published October 2018, <https://www.iea.org/reports/20-renewable-energy-policy-recommendations>.

		(TNC), Ocean Conservancy , Sierra Club , World Resources Institute , World Wildlife Fund (WWF) Bellona
Industry	Related to breakwater construction & FPV; structural integrity tools users, engineers, project developers, FPV technology providers, financial institutions, insurance entities, installers, O&M entities, local marine industries, Marine leisure activities	Fisheries, tourism
Citizenship	Individuals that are members in a specific region or state.	Being an EU project it is necessary to generalise this stakeholder group – having to include the citizens of every European country. Limitations are not beneficiary.
Research and academic	Circular material researchers and students. Academic community: SUREWAVE will reach postgraduates, but also for future research and innovation collaborations in the opened research lines.	<p>Journals Frontiers in Marine Science, Journal of Marine Science & Engineering, Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures, Ocean Engineering Applied Ocean Research, Applied Sciences, Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, International Journal of Concrete Structure and Materials, Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics</p> <p>Conferences International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference – ISOPE International Conference on Ocean, Offshore & Arctic Engineering – OMAE</p>

		Solar Energy Expo Floating Solar PV Forum Marine Energy Week
Media	Private or publish media institutions. Limitations and plans are suggested in Newsletters and Press Releases section. This particular stakeholder category is dynamic and interest will have to be evaluated continuously during the project.	List of possible media clusters can be found under Annex X.

2. Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication Plan

According to the Grant Agreements point 1.2.8 (Data Management and Management of other Research Outputs) 'SUREWAVE will ensure research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR data principle)' [1]. The Data Management Plan (DMP)(D1.3) covers this in more detail.

To comply with Horizon Europe Open Science requirements research findings are published on Zenodo (EC-funded initiative supporting the Open Access policy). Data is uploaded and stored in CERN's Data Centre, automatically becoming a part of OpenAIRE. All research is easily searchable and cited according to an assigned Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Zenodo arrange stored data in communities, i.e., categories. Henceforth, creating a new community for the Surewave project under the Horizon Europe umbrella is required.

Strategic implementation

This section is central to this document; a single individual might make strategic plans that are second to none, but without sufficient implementation, they won't be any good. The same goes for this document. Moving in the same direction – towards common dissemination, exploitation, and communication goals is imperative, and steps for implementation may look like this⁷:

- Defining the goals is the first step
- Determining roles and responsibilities.
- Delegating the work
- Execute the plan. Measure and evaluate
- Make adjustments where needed
- Get closure on the project
- Review end-result

⁷ Kelsey Miller, "A MANAGER'S GUIDE TO SUCCESSFUL STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION," Harvard Business School Online, Published February 2020, <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/strategy-implementation-for-managers>.

Subtask 8.2.1 Internal Communication Training will be utilized as a Strategic DECMP implementation session. A digital Google Meet is planned for M8 to discuss and plan according to the first revision of the DEC master plan. Feedback from the consortium members is encouraged, and implementation of changes will happen continuously.

Dissemination, Exploitation & Communication routes

The project will actively engage with its stakeholders through various dissemination routes, which will be discussed in the section below. They cover multiple digital channels, various printed documents, physical conferences, -events and meetings, webinars, general collaborations between relevant projects, and dialogue with the EU community at large.

The suggested routes will include different activities.

The activities will be measured between month 6 (M6) and the second revision of the DEC master plan in month 18 (M18). Afterward, they will continue to the end of the project.

If needed the collected data will enable adjustments or refocusing of efforts in M18. Reports on both webpage performance and social media will be conducted monthly. Relevant key performance indicators are listed under each route category. The measurement tools will be accounted for below.

Online Presence: Project Website & Social Media

The domain for the SUREWAVE project (<https://surewave.eu/>) is established to form the collaborative platform for the project. It is intended as the tree trunk of the communication tree, with different branches that lead to other platforms (routes). The webpage is expected to be relevant to most of our stakeholders. It is developed in GitHub and is administered by SLS.

Picture: SUREWAVE homepage

Through the webpage we will aim to:

- Generate 12,000/year web visits, >36.000 in total by cross-linking and SEO
- Inform stakeholders about the purpose, and scope of Surewave

- Build awareness and knowledge about the project and its benefits to society and industry.
- Update followers once newsletters are released.
- Redirect readers to the social media channels to obtain additional content and to start following actively (if they have not already done so).
- To direct readers to [Zenodo](#) to obtain in-depth project results and research, not covered on the web or in the newsletters.

As important milestones are completed newsletters will be released and notifications forwarded to those interested. Upon release, designated posts on social media channels will help direct readers to the homepage. Newsletters are explained in further detail in this document.

Social Media

Social media is covered through LinkedIn, Twitter, and Youtube. LinkedIn and Twitter are suitable channels to notify users actively pursuing information and updates frequently. They both represent hubs that gather large communities that, to a large degree, have awareness and knowledge about the industry and research. The social media channels will aim to:

- Reach 500 followers on Twitter + LinkedIn
- To build a community with active members that interact through dialogue and with the content on the channels.
- Post 6+ infographics, 3 factsheets

<https://www.linkedin.com/company/surewave/>

A channel for video content (Youtube) is also established to upload and share effectively. 2 videos (intro and final) will be produced to summarise the results. Production for the first video is planned for the second consortium meeting in San Sebastian, 18-19th of April.

Publication of Journal Articles

Sharing our research findings is arguably our most crucial communication route due to the immense journal article industry that exists online. As briefly discussed under 'Online Presence: Project Website & Social Media', Journal Articles will be published on our webpage under the 'News' tab. The primary targeted stakeholders will be researchers and academics. Publishing open data to open access sources (like Zenodo) will be our primary source of sharing content for the research community. These platforms have a superior reach potential in already established communities with significant trustworthiness. Furthermore, most of them have significant followers on their social media platforms. However, the criteria must be that it is *open access*, *i.e.*, users are not required to pay to review the content. Our goals for this route will be to:

- Produce 6+ articles of peer-reviewed research papers, submitted on the project webpage, [Zenodo](#) and other open-access scientific platforms.
- 300 academics reached
- 140 citations

- Subtask: produce a Technical Brochure. SINTEF & SIS will write a 20+ page technical brochure for industry stakeholders summarising the results, which will include graphics and photographs
- Get coverage through uploads on science sharing, but moreover on their social media channel: Zenodo Twitter > 7778 followers worldwide.

Target Journals (Index-factor):

- Frontiers in Marine Science (4.435)
- Journal of Marine Science & Engineering (2.458)
- Mechanics of Advanced Materials and Structures (4.03)
- Ocean Engineering (3.795)
- Applied Ocean Research (2.979)
- Applied Sciences (2.679)
- Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews (14.982)
- International Journal of Concrete Structure and Materials (3.2)
- Engineering Applications of Computational Fluid Mechanics

Scientific Conferences

The SUREWAVE project will aim to participate in external events, e.g., conferences and fairs, throughout its lifetime. These venues represent a central arena to reach out to the academic community: hereunder material, aero & hydrodynamics, structural integrity, monitoring, predictive tools, offshore energy structure industries, and energy utilities. Conferences and fairs also present an opportunity to interact with stakeholders outside the digital sphere to build brand authenticity. The notion is that project results and milestones will be presented through oral presentations or stand with printed materials, i.e., posters, leaflets, or brochures.

Our key performance indicators for this route are:

- To produce and conduct 10 presentations.
- Facilitating 3 conference workshops > reaching 250 experts in total.

Among the targeted events are:

- International Ocean and Polar Engineering Conference – ISOPE
- International Conference on Ocean, Offshore & Arctic Engineering – OMAE
- Solar Energy Expo
- Floating Solar PV Forum
- Marine Energy Week

The SUREWAVE Conference will be held towards the end of the project, presenting the final research and its impacts. Our primary KPI for the event is to engage with >100 stakeholders.

Workshops

As stated in the Grand Agreement a stakeholder advisory board (SAB) will be established, task 2.4. Two workshops are planned, and the first results will be presented in the second revision of the DEC in M18. In terms of communication, these SAB workshops intend to open dialogue with stakeholders, create

mutual understanding and engage in active listening. Transparency and physical interaction will hopefully build awareness, knowledge and inclination to the technology and industry.

Success depends on our ability to identify meaningful stakeholders, open dialogue, and understand their needs and challenges in light of SUREWAVES' life-cycle assessment (LCA).

Interactions with other EC-funded Projects/Clusters

Exchanging key,- and common learnings to create synergies is essential for optimal results. Cross-project interaction will help strengthen informed decision-making on where to focus efforts and where not to waste resources. Upon invitation by the CINEA, the consortium will contribute to common information and dissemination activities to increase the visibility and synergies between Horizon Europe-supported actions.

As part of the clustering interaction, SUREWAVE took part in the EU-funded Naturesea-PV Public Kick-Off Workshop on March 15th. Other relevant EU associations and events are BRIDGE, Solar Power Europe, Ocean Energy Europe. WP8 lead participated in the first cluster interaction event in March 2023, the BRIDGE 2023 General Assembly.

Our key performance indicators for this route are:

- To host/interact at two joint events > leading to 100 new contacts from science, wastewater recovery, and biorefineries

Media coverage

This communication route is closely linked to the press release production. WP leader will actively reach media clusters before essential milestones and events, primarily through press releases. According to the Grant Agreement point 17.1, the beneficiaries must promote the action towards the media unless otherwise agreed. The granted authority must be informed in advance when activities are expected to have a significant media impact.

We have been discussing owned media routes – i.e., media established and administered by consortium members. Media coverage includes *deserved* media – i.e., organic recognition from media, once something is deemed newsworthy. Secondly, there is paid search or paid promotion.

Therefore, a limitation is needed. Media outlets must be open access, and no financial incentives should be included to get coverage.

Media coverage between M0-M6:

Norwegian SciTech News –

<https://gemini.no/2022/11/skal-gjore-det-mulig-med-flytende-sol-i-nordsjoen/>

Communication types

Films, Videos

Video content will be created and used for multiple communication routes—one promotional video at the beginning and one towards the end of the project. The first intention is to present the project visually and comprehensively, followed by a summary video that embodies the final technical results.

While striving to convey research, it makes sense to differentiate the marketing and communication mix. Even data-heavy, quantitative studies have visual aspects that resonate with people. It creates context and helps followers understand complex academic themes. Utilizing the visual elements of the project is, therefore, a goal.

Print

Different types of content will be delivered, including various posters and roll-ups, one flyer, and one technical brochure. Printed material will be used for conferences and fairs. A brochure will be developed in a collaboration between SLS and SINTEF with a total of 20 pages, aimed at industry stakeholders and summarizing the technical results and methodologies. This will happen in M36. It will also include graphics and photographs. The KPI for the technical brochure is to reach 2,000 industry stakeholders and potential adopters of SUREWAVE solutions.

Newsletters & press releases

Newsletters will be published every sixth month – five newsletters in total. They will be covering the progress of the project and general updates related to the project. The opening newsletter will be released in April 2023, after the consortium has met for its six-month meeting in San Sebastian. In addition to newsletters, general news updates may be published if it is considered beneficial and urgent to post them separately. The consortium will be requested to participate during the production of newsletters, either through status meetings, content sharing or short interviews.

The 'News' section will also be preferred for journalistic articles and scientific interviews.

Articles

Described under section: Publication of Articles.

Progress Reports

SINTEF is the lead beneficiary of the Grand Agreements Deliverable 1.2 - Interim progress reports. 2 intermediate Progress Reports between the official complete Periodic Reports. There will be a second one in M25. Associated to Task 1.1 Hereunder, progress for the DEC initiatives is covered. This is aimed to inform internal stakeholders. Newsletters are external progress reports that will inform external stakeholder groups.

Presentations

Presentations will be produced for multiple purposes, both digitally and physically. Along with communication material in general, the consortium has to acknowledge the EU in all of its' content. This is covered in 17.2 Visibility — European flag and funding statement. Templates for presentations will be located in SINTEF's SharePoint. Moreover, measures are required to comply with EU guidelines for visual identity⁸.

⁸ European Commission, "European Commission Visual Identity," Commission.europa.eu, Last accessed March 2023, https://commission.europa.eu/resources-partners/european-commission-visual-identity_en.

Key Messages for different stakeholder groups

Primary stakeholder groups	Key message
Industry	EU seas has enormous potential and floating PV is a reliable and efficient source of energy, ideal to benefit from it. The breakwater development makes it possible to utilize vast areas which would otherwise be difficult to utilize.
Research/academics	Ground-breaking R&D has been funded by the EU Commission, diversifying the renewable energy portfolio. Publish research papers under the framework of globally recognized scientific journals and conferences that count with a high impact index. ⁹
Citizenship	Estimated energy savings and greenhouse gas reductions ¹⁰ . Floating PV and breakwater structures are safe and sustainable solutions. The floating breakwaters could also be used in other applications such as fish farming
Investors	Experts have estimated that the total worldwide capacity of FPV could reach 62 GW by 2030 ¹¹ , making this a potentially booming industry for the future.
Policy makers	SURWAVE will engage (through Task 2.4) policymakers and financial institutions to increase awareness of FPV systems that can lead to increased support for investing in R&D and deployment projects and that will raise sufficient background, in FPV and its benefits to allow policymakers to design effective policies and regulations.
EU commission / EU network	The consortium is actively collaborating with the EU community and engaging in sister projects and organizations to amplify the visibility and impact of the project.
NGOs	The project will prioritize the use of low-carbon materials for the FPV and will ensure not to substantially affect marine ecosystems. In addition, the solution is aimed to generate

⁹ EU Commission, "Structural reliable offshore floating PV solution integrating circular concrete floating breakwater," GRANT AGREEMENT Project 101083342, SUREWAVE. Last accessed March 2023.

¹⁰ United States Environmental Protection Agency, "Engaging Stakeholders in Climate and Clean Energy Policy," EPA.gov, Last modified March 2023, https://19january2017snapshot.epa.gov/statelocalclimate/engaging-stakeholders-climate-and-clean-energy-policy_.html.

¹¹ Leadvent Group, "The State of Floating PV in Europe and Asia," Leadventgrp.com, Last modified March 2023, <https://www.leadventgrp.com/blog/the-state-of-floating-pv-in-europe-and-asia>.

	renewable electricity contributing to climate change mitigation and a reduction of pollution in coastal areas.
Media	Sustainable Development Goals (SDG): SUREWAVE aims to unlock massive deployment of offshore FPV. It is not only contributing to the scientific impact, but also to the economic and societal impact, addressing the 9 Key Impact Pathways (KIPs) defined by HORIZON EUROPE and contributing to the following Sustainable Development Goals: SDG-7. Affordable and Clean Energy, SDG-8. Decent Work and Economic Growth, SDG-9. Industry, Innovation & Infrastructure, SDG-12. Responsible Consumption and Production and SDG-13. Climate Action.

3. Data Security

Refer to the Data Management Plan (DMP deliverable D1.3) for details. According to the Grant Agreement: ‘The beneficiaries must manage the digital research data generated in the action (‘data’) responsibly, in line with the FAIR principles.¹² ; making sure the generated data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. A more description of Data security is provided in D1.3: Data Management Plan.

4. Conclusions

Strategic implementation of the DECMP and tactical measures is central to reaping the benefits of the activities. Therefore, workshops and online sessions will be conducted to create awareness and ownership within the consortium. A great deal of effort will be made to make the suggested involvement relevant to each consortium member. Since every participant has their own deliverables and focus area, the WP lead will carefully plan and prepare task delegation to minimize unnecessary bureaucracy. Furthermore, effective channels for internal communication and cross-collaborating sister projects are important for project exploitability. The benefits of the established EU network and knowledge sharing may lead to positive synergies.

To evaluate the measures and results of the DECMP in a meaningful way, we need to address the strategic goals for impact, stated in the Grand Agreement. These goals address specific areas of interest and by default, also indicate primary stakeholder groups.

Goal 1: *Raising awareness and informing*

¹² EU Commission. “STRUCTURAL RELIABLE OFFSHORE FLOATING PV SOLUTION INTEGRATING CIRCULAR CONCRETE FLOATING BREAKWATER.” GRANT AGREEMENT Project 101083342, SUREWAVE. Last accessed March 2023. P 11.

The primary stakeholder groups that need to build awareness and knowledge about the project are external stakeholders. These are research/academics, industry, policy-makers, NGOs, and citizens. The media is considered a secondary stakeholder that is critical to utilize, in order to enable optimal impact, especially towards certain groups like the citizens. This group is not actively engaging with

the project and is not present on many of the selected communication routes. To build awareness and knowledge among citizens it is, therefore, necessary to succeed with media interest and coverage. In order to make impactful communication, we have addressed key messages for each stakeholder segment. Actively using and refining these key messages as we learn underway is important. This requires that the consortium exchange knowledge and that the DECMP is used as an interactive tool.

Goal 2: *Engaging in a dialogue*

To succeed with the dialogue externally, we need to create effective synergies internally. Proper implementation of strategic DECMP is essential to move in the same direction as a group. We also want to utilize the unique opportunity that a consortium offers, through accumulated knowledge and already established stakeholder relations. SUREWAVE members need to open and maintain dialogue to exploit potential opportunities on a weekly basis. Central routes are Microsoft Teams, Email, and workshops both digitally and physically (including 6M meetings). WP8 lead is central to succeed with the execution through weekly and monthly follow-up, in addition to documenting the development and learning in the second iteration of the DECMP (M18). Establishing relations and routines internally will solidify the basis on which we communicate externally, as a group.

Furthermore, frequent and varied (external) stakeholder dialogue is considered key to achieving long-term project sustainability. Effectively communicating the relevance to these stakeholders will be imperative, e.g., making them understand *why* it matters to them. Active listening, identifying needs, and understanding our projects' role in it is central. Our presence will be conducted in both the physical and digital spheres. Workshops (round-table), conferences, and fairs are still great forums to interact with many of our stakeholders. Being clear on what we want to achieve by doing it, and more importantly, what we will not do. Should stakeholders expect us to change certain parts of the research after engaging in dialogue, or are we interacting due to other purposes? Henceforth, the criteria for success are transparency and the ability to communicate how our data will be incorporated into our research project. This will strengthen our stance and help create meaningful and credible discussions with optimal frames to foster exploitation opportunities.

Goal 3: *Transferring knowledge*

In many ways, this goal is an extension of goal 1. This entails that we are somewhat dependent on successfully building awareness and knowledge about the project to effectively transfer knowledge, at least with some of the stakeholders. Creating traction early on in the project is therefore important.

The SUREWAVE proposal clearly states that there is a **'clear and huge opportunity in the research and development'**, and that **'Floating Photo-Voltaic (FPV) is in the early R&D stage when it comes to open sea deployment'**. This underlines the importance of the research/academic stakeholder groups in the project, also bearing in mind that open science and open innovation form one of the project's main pillars¹³.

¹³ EU Commission, "Structural reliable offshore floating PV solution integrating circular concrete floating breakwater," Proposal Project 101083342, SUREWAVE, Last accessed March 2023, P. 16,

Primary dissemination and communication measures are believed to be documentation of research through world recognised, open data routes. It is a channel with vast potential in terms of unique users and the channels' large degree of credibility.

Furthermore, local public authorities are often responsible for adapting and implementing new research and technology¹⁴. This might be a promising route to the SUREWAVE project in terms of communication and exploitation. According to the Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy:

Public authorities should therefore plan this long-term developments early on, assessing their environmental, social and economic sustainability, ensuring coexistence with other activities, such as fisheries and aquaculture, shipping, tourism, defence or infrastructure deployment, and making sure the public accept planned deployments.

Public authorities are therefore also highlighted as a *primary stakeholders*. The project has to build awareness among local government, before proceeding with knowledge transfer, which will enable planning and adoption.

Goal 4: Increasing acceptance

The primary objective of this goal is to reduce the uncertainty surrounding the technical solution and answer environmental and cost benefit questions. This merges with the previous goal of building knowledge. Clear communication surrounding maritime spatial planning needs to be brought forth in our channels, which is believed to be of importance to several key stakeholder groups like NGOs, policy providers, economic actors, and citizenship at large¹⁵.

For instance, coastal Member States in the EU are obliged to deliver marine spatial plans as part of the environmental assessment. Complying with procedures and communicating these aspects of the project might solidify the credibility towards stakeholders.

There are no plans to date of measuring how prone these groups are to technology. However, this interweaves with Deliverable D7.6 – Report on integrated sustainability assessment. In terms of measurement, this document will not go into further detail on the measurement of this goal.

Goal 5: Replicating the SUREWAVE solutions

The ability to replicate is dependent on documentation and a clear, transparent process behind decision-making. The ability to successfully execute each impact strategy goal paves way for the next, from early awareness-making, knowledge-building, acceptance, and stakeholder dialogue. The intention is that documentation will start early, including: 'research outputs e.g., publications, data, software, models, algorithms, components' designs, material mixes'¹⁶.

Furthermore, assisting the EU with its overall communication objectives and awareness work may prove necessary in terms of future exploitation pathways. SUREWAVE as a project is completely dependent on public knowledge of EU regulations and economic incentives. The EU Offshore Renewable Energy Strategy discusses how to mobilise private-sector investment in marine renewables:

¹⁴ European Commission, "An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future," Energy.ec.europa.eu, Last modified March 2023, p7, https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-11/offshore_renewable_energy_strategy_0.pdf.

¹⁵ European Commission, "An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future," Energy.ec.europa.eu, Last modified March 2023, p10,

¹⁶ EU Commission, "Structural reliable offshore floating PV solution integrating circular concrete floating breakwater," Proposal Project 101083342, SUREWAVE, Last accessed March 2023, p16.

For less mature technologies, or projects still, at an early stage, EU public funding will be crucial for market creation, by bringing on board more private actors, improving competitiveness, reducing uncertainties, bringing down costs, and accelerating progress on early deployment and commercialisation.

An important part of our communication and exploitation plan will therefore be to contextualize matters like EU funding programmes.

5. Limitations

The first iteration of the DECMP has completed a general screening of stakeholder groups, however, certain groups are expected to be more critical than others. Hence, some of the clusters will be awarded a larger degree of effort and resources. This will result in a limitation of our understanding of some clusters within given categories, which might be ironic. Having a granted amount of resources sometimes involves making informed assumptions, which prevent us from having absolute certainty in every aspect of our decision-making.

Nevertheless, having an open approach to our communication enables us to respond to stakeholder development during the project, which may entail including clusters that we assumed weren't relevant or important during the early evaluation stages. Arguably there will always be a degree of uncertainty and limitation involved when one communicates, due to ever-changing sociodemographic factors that will be based on small changes in the SUREWAVE project's current scope.

As previously mentioned, in terms of media coverage we will focus on *deserved media* coverage, which is open access to comply with our project's FAIR principles.

Bibliography, References

The following list summarizes applicable rules and regulations, standards, recommendations, and other relevant references. Unless otherwise noted, standards and guidelines are applied in their latest revision/edition.

1. Barney, Nick. "What is a stakeholder?." Techtarger.com. Last modified January 2023. <https://www.techtarger.com/searchcio/definition/stakeholder>.
2. European Commission. "Corporate social responsibility & Responsible business conduct." Commission.europa.eu. Last modified March 2023. https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/sustainability/corporate-social-responsibility-responsible-business-conduct_en.
3. IEA. "20 Renewable Energy Policy Recommendations." IEA. Published October 2018. <https://www.iea.org/reports/20-renewable-energy-policy-recommendations>.
4. Miller, Kelsey. "A MANAGER'S GUIDE TO SUCCESSFUL STRATEGY IMPLEMENTATION." Harvard Business School Online. Published February 2020. <https://online.hbs.edu/blog/post/strategy-implementation-for-managers>.

5. Matomo. "What data does Matomo track?." Matomo.org. Last modified March 2023. https://matomo.org/faq/general/faq_18254/.
6. EU Commission. "STRUCTURAL RELIABLE OFFSHORE FLOATING PV SOLUTION INTEGRATING CIRCULAR CONCRETE FLOATING BREAKWATER." GRANT AGREEMENT Project 101083342, SUREWAVE. Last accessed March 2023.
7. United States Environmental Protection Agency. "Engaging Stakeholders in Climate and Clean Energy Policy." EPA.gov. Last modified March 2023. https://19january2017snapshot.epa.gov/statelocalclimate/engaging-stakeholders-climate-and-clean-energy-policy_.html.
8. Leadvent Group. "The State of Floating PV in Europe and Asia." Leadventgrp.com. Last modified March 2023. <https://www.leadventgrp.com/blog/the-state-of-floating-pv-in-europe-and-asia>.
9. EU Commission. "Structural reliable offshore floating PV solution integrating circular concrete floating breakwater." Proposal Project 101083342, SUREWAVE. Last accessed March 2023. *HE_SUREWAVE_Proposal_v5.pdf.
10. European Commission. "An EU Strategy to harness the potential of offshore renewable energy for a climate neutral future." Energy.ec.europa.eu. Last modified. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-11/offshore_renewable_energy_strategy_0.pdf.
11. Collins English Dictionary. "Definition of 'target group'." Collinsdictionary.com. Last modified March 2023. <https://www.collinsdictionary.com/dictionary/english/target-group>.
12. European Commission. "European Commission Visual Identity." Commission.europa.eu. Last accessed March 2023. https://commission.europa.eu/resources-partners/european-commission-visual-identity_en.